

EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL INVESTIGATION OF MIXED-MODE FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION

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Bladed disks (or ‘blisks’) are often subjected to foreign object damage which may result in the initiation of cracks. Cracks in aero-engine blisks are affected by a combination of loads which propagate a crack in a multiaxial stress field. Depending on the local stress field, a crack may propagate through the blade, or more undesirably grow towards the bore of the disc due to hoop stress. A test rig and Ti-6Al-4V cruciform test sample have been designed and built to capture the key features of crack propagation in a blisk. The results of the experiments will enable modification and validation of a crack growth model. Experimental results correlate reasonably well with predictions from the maximum tensile stress criterion, in both trajectory and crack growth rate, and demonstrate the influence of hoop stress on the crack trajectory in a blisk.

Keywords: Multiaxial fatigue, non-proportional loading

INTRODUCTION

Blisks in aero-engines are affected by a combination of loads which grow a crack in a multiaxial stress field. Depending on the local stress field, a crack may propagate through the blade, or more undesirably grow towards the bore of the disc due to hoop stress. The overall trajectories of cracks initiating near the base of the blade are particularly difficult to predict.

Whilst early crack growth models were effective for predicting growth in mode-I, cracks in real structures are often subjected to a mixture of mode-I, II and III loads. Loading is considered to be proportional if the principal stress directions remain constant during a cycle. Thus, non-proportional loading may be produced by superimposing cyclic and static loads which each contribute a different mixture of modes [1]. Existing crack growth criterion such as the maximum tensile stress criterion (MTS) and maximum shear stress criterion (MSS) are able to provide accurate predictions proportionally loaded for 2D cracks in certain materials. The MTS criterion, presented in Eqn 1, was proposed by Erdogan and Sih [2] and assumes that crack growth occurs in the direction which is perpendicular to the maximum tangential stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ at the crack tip.

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\Delta K_I \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - \frac{3}{2} \Delta K_{II} \sin(\theta) \right] \quad (1)$$

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Non-proportional loading occurs when a crack is loaded in a mixed-mode scheme where the modes are not in phase. This results in a varying R-ratio so criteria based on ΔK alone are not always valid. Fatemi and Shamsaei [3] completed fatigue tests on cylindrical test specimens under tension (mode-I) and torsion (mode-II). 90° Out-of-phase loading resulted in a higher crack growth rate and fewer cracks growing. The higher growth rate was explained by a higher normal stress occurring on the maximum shear plane in out-of-phase loading. A similar result was obtained by Yu, Li and Proust [4] who observed mixed mode-I and II crack growth in tubular specimens of aluminium alloy 7076-T651. Thirteen non-proportional load cycles were tested. Additionally, the authors found that loading two specimens with load cycles which were identical but reversed in direction (clockwise and anti-clockwise) resulted in drastically different crack growth rates.

Attempts have been made at modelling crack growth in compressor blades. Mangardich et al [5] compare simulated crack growth in FRANC3D with fractured compressor aerofoils. The aerofoils, made from Ti-6Al-4V were subjected to LCF loads from rotation and heat, and HCF loads from bending. The authors concluded from fractographic analysis of aerofoil fracture surfaces that HCF was predominantly responsible for crack growth. Simulated cracks grown under only LCF loading did not match the fractured samples in direction or shape. The HCF crack growth was accelerated by the LCF load since it imposed a positive mean stress on the dynamic bending load, however the LCF cycles themselves did not make a significant contribution. The authors found that LEFM and the MTS criterion predicted the crack direction accurately, which has also been recognised previous studies on crack growth in Ti-6Al-4V blades [6]. However, Mangardich notes that in many previous studies conducted on blades with dovetail attachments, damping reduces the effect of the vibratory stresses. Byrne et al [7] identified that in Ti-6Al-4V specimens, a crack would initially propagate in LCF until the HCF threshold was reached. Overloading the specimen prior to dynamic loading reduced the effect of HCF. A hybrid approach to modelling was used by Witek [8] to model a compressor blade subject to resonant vibration. The blade was modelled analytically using a simplified rectangular geometry and the Raju-Newman equations on a half elliptical crack. The model used a Paris growth law to estimate a 29% greater lifetime than the experimental results from the blade. The discrepancy may be explained by oversimplification of the blade geometry. The analytical model only considered crack growth when the blade was displaced to the pressure side which could also lead to a less conservative lifetime estimate.

To create an improved crack trajectory criterion, a series of fatigue tests have been carried out on representative Ti-6Al-4V test samples to build a database of experimental results. The test rig and a cruciform shaped test samples have been designed to capture the key features of crack propagation in a blisk. Specimens may be loaded in three axes using a biaxial machine and hydraulic fixture. This arrangement aims to reproduce the combination of steady and dynamic loads in a crack in a blisk. The ratio of the applied loads has been determined from fatigue simulations in FRANC3D, a software package which simulates crack growth using linear elastic fracture mechanics. The results of the completed tests will help to update the crack growth model to gain an agreement between the simulated and experimental results of the test specimen. The final crack growth model will be used to accurately predict the trajectory of cracks initiating in blisks subjected to non-proportional loading.

METHODS

Loads in the blisk have been categorised as steady or cyclic. Rotational body forces have been considered steady, and vibrational loads have been considered cyclic. Of the vibrational loads, only

the mode shape of the first vibration mode (first flap) has been considered. Loading conditions may vary depending on the location of crack initiation site. A crack which initiates at a high position on the fillet between the blade and disc will propagate axially across the blade, while a crack initiating in the lower region of the fillet may propagate towards the bore due to the influence of hoop stresses.

Test specimen design

A cruciform specimen and biaxial test rig have been designed to replicate the loading conditions in a crack in a blisk. The first flap vibration mode results in a cyclic bending load across the thickness of the blade. The test rig in Figure 1 replicates the stress state around the crack in the blisk in a cruciform specimen with cracks inserted at 45° in the internal filleted corners. The dimensions and positions of the notch geometries used in this test series are illustrated in Figure 3. The radial stress in the blisk is replicated by a constant tension from a biaxial machine actuator (z-axis in Figure 2). The hoop stress is replicated by a constant tension supplied by a fixture which houses a pressurised hydraulic cylinder (x-axis in Figure 2). The cyclic bending load is replicated by a four-point bending setup which consists of 4 pairs of loading pins.

Crack growth was simulated using an iterative meshing method with the software package FRANC3D. Specimens were modelled as 3D solids and split into a global model and local model. In the local model, crack fronts were modelled using wedge elements (C3D15) around the crack front which were surrounded by brick elements (C3D20). The majority of the mesh outside the crack front was formed of coarse tetrahedral elements which were interfaced with the brick elements through a layer of pyramid elements. Local effects of the EDM process, such as damage in the recast layer, were not considered in the model. Multiple initiation sites have been observed along some starter notches. However, the initiation sites from which most growth has occurred are evident from fractography, which has informed subsequent simulations. Typical crack growth models were formed of 60,000 elements after the insertion of a crack. Since remeshing was used to model the advancing of crack fronts, element numbers increased as cracks grew larger. The results discussed in this paper featured 210,000 elements at the point of fracture.

FIGURE 1 (a) Cruciform specimen and loading arms (b) Centre of specimen with EDM starter edge notch (c) Hydraulic cylinder arrangement.

FIGURE 2 Cruciform specimen loading scheme.

FIGURE 3 (a) Notch locations. Dimensions of (b) corner notch at location 1 and (c) edge notch at location 1.

Tests configurations

A series of 10 tests have been performed on cruciform specimens. The chemical composition of the Ti-6Al-4V specimens is presented in Table 1. Tests were also completed on five trial specimens of mild steel (S275). In each specimen, a number of starter notches were inserted into the internal filleted corners at the center of the specimen. In six specimens, starter notches were 3 mm long and cut towards the centre of the specimen with an EDM wire oriented in the through-thickness direction. In four specimens, corner notches were cut into the edge of the fillets with an EDM wire oriented 45° from the through thickness towards the centre of the specimen. The loading schemes and notch configurations for each test are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of Ti-6Al-4V specimens

Element	Ti	Al	V	Fe	O	C	N	H
Composition (wt %)	Balance	5.78	3.92	0.11	0.128	0.019	0.012	0.001

TABLE 2 Summary of test configurations

Test number	Material	Load (kN)			Notch type	Notch locations
		x	y, (R = -1)	z		
0.1	Mild steel S275	8.7	14.5	30.1	Corner	1 - 8
0.2	Mild steel S275	15.4	9.7	20.1	Through-thickness	1 - 4
0.3	Mild steel S275	15.4	9.7	13.4	Through-thickness	1 - 4
0.4	Mild steel S275	15.4	9.7	13.4	Through-thickness	1, 3
0.5	Mild steel S275	15.4	9.7	13.4	Through-thickness	1, 3
1	Ti-6Al-4V	8.7	14.5	20.1	Corner	1 - 8
2	Ti-6Al-4V	15.4	9.7	20.1	Through-thickness	1 - 4
3	Ti-6Al-4V	15.4	9.7	20.1	Through-thickness	1
4	Ti-6Al-4V	15.4	9.7	13.4	Corner	1, 3
5	Ti-6Al-4V	15.4	9.7	10.0	Corner	1, 3

RESULTS

Optical micrographs

Fracture surfaces of the completed tests have been observed through optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figure 4 illustrates the location of the scanned fracture surfaces in a broken cruciform specimen. Surfaces have been plotted in the coordinate system used in Figure 2.

FIGURE 4 Processing of fractured specimens.

In all specimens which had 4 through-thickness notches, two crack initiated at corners which were located on the same surface of the plate (equal position in y), with both cracks coalescing before the final fracture of the specimen. In specimens 0.2 and 2 crack growth proceeded on an expected trajectory from the corner where crack initiation first occurred. The second crack, which initiated in the adjacent corner, grew in the opposing direction. The crack faces of these tests are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5a shows crack initiation in four corners of the fracture surface from Test 0.2, indicated by beach marks. Major cracks have propagated along the lower edge until they have coalesced. A region of fast fracture is present at the center of the surface and a shear lip has formed on the upper edge during the final fracture. In Figure 5b, the fatigue features on the fracture surface of Test 2 are less easily interpreted due to the highly faceted surface. Cracks have coalesced in the lower region of the face, indicating crack growth from the lower corners. Ratchet marks are present along the left and right edges. A small shear lip has formed on the upper edge and a less streaked texture is visible in the upper region. The textural change across the surface corroborates with the expected regions of fatigue crack growth at the corners and area of fast fracture in the upper region. In the lower left and lower right regions, where cracks are expected to have initiated and grown, parallel facets are more visible than elsewhere on the surface. The crack initiating in the lower right corner has grown further before the final fracture.

FIGURE 5 Fracture surfaces from (a) Test 0.2 and (b) Test 2.

Fracture surface measurement

Fracture surfaces from Tests 0.2 and 2 have been photographed and their depth measured using focus variation with an optical microscope (Alicona InfiniteFocus G4). The measurement resolution is $11\ \mu\text{m}$ in the x and y directions and $0.05\ \mu\text{m}$ in the vertical direction.

FIGURE 6 Fracture surface depth measurements of (a) Test 0.2 and (b) Test 2.

The predicted trajectory for test 2 is shown in Figure 7a and the relative error between the prediction and result is plotted in Figure 7b. The black region denotes the area of fast fracture, and the coloured region denotes areas of fatigue crack growth where K_I has not exceeded the critical stress intensity factor $50 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. The predicted trajectory in assumes equal crack growth in the MTS criterion from two through-thickness starter cracks. Although the bending loading is fully reversed across the principal axis $y = 0$, crack growth occurs from only the lower corners. This is due to increased bending stresses occurring at this edge after initial crack initiation, and this asymmetry is naturally replicated in the simulation. The cracked specimen may be more accurately modelled using blunt through-thickness notches and quarter-elliptical starter cracks inserted into each notch at the lower corner. However, this complicates the meshing of the crack front as one edge of it must ‘stick’ to the concave face of the notch as it grows. The modelling method predicts two raised regions visible at $y = 0$, where the crack front abruptly bends, but otherwise shows a similar trend in crack growth trajectory to the experimental result. The error plot in Figure 7b shows that the trajectories of the right and left cracks have opposing errors relative to the prediction. Errors in the in the right crack front are generally smaller and consistently around 40%.

FIGURE 7 Test 2 (a) predicted trajectory and (b) comparison to experimental result.

Figure 8 shows the crack geometry of test 2 and the corresponding predicted trajectory taken at two section planes. In Figure 8a a section is taken at the plane $y = -7.4$ mm, which is spaced 0.1 mm from the lower edge to avoid measurement artifacts. Figure 8b displays the crack at the section plane $y = 5.0$ mm. In Figure 8a it is clear that the MTS criterion provides an accurate prediction of the trajectory of the right crack for small crack sizes. The predicted deflection is within 10% of the experimental result until the crack length exceeds 3.1 mm. Outside of this range the relative error from the experimental result increases linearly to the point that the cracks coalesce. The left crack has deflected by 45% of the prediction and it is possible that its initial trajectory has been affected by the prior initiation and growth of the right crack. SEM imaging of the fracture surface has shown that both crack fronts have grown in fatigue to the point that they combined and fast fracture occurred after this. However, the trajectories in the central region may not be effectively modelled by the MTS criterion due to the loss of the small-scale yielding condition.

FIGURE 8 Crack geometry viewed at section planes (a) $y = -7.4$ mm and (b) $y = -5.0$ mm.

SEM fractographs

SEM images of the fracture surface have been taken at several points to compare crack growth rates with the MTS model. The tensile stress in the cruciform in the z direction is summed from the effects of the bending load ($R = -1$) and tensile loads applied in the y and z axes respectively. Because of this, the effective R -ratio at the surfaces of the specimen may be considered to be -0.60 . A series of SEM micrographs (Figure 9) have been captured at locations along the specimen edge to compare the crack growth rate calculated from striation spacing to that predicted by the MTS model. The Walker model has been found to provide reasonable fatigue life predictions using a Walker fitting constant, $\gamma = 0.5431$ [9], [10]. Paris growth law constants ($C_0 = 1.02 \times 10^{-10}$, $m = 2.50$) have been determined from separate tests. The comparison of the ΔK_I values in TABLE 3 shows a reasonable correlation between MTS and experimental data. It should be noted that locations sampled near $x = 0$ are not well aligned to the MTS due to asymmetry of the cracks in the specimen. At location F, the tabulated MTS value is of ΔK_I that of the midpoint where both cracks are modelled to coalesce.

TABLE 3 Comparison of ΔK_I derived from striation spacing and MTS model

Location	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Striation spacing (μm)	Experimental ΔK_I ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)	Predicted ΔK_I ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)
A	-13.04	7.21	0.082	14.2	19.9
B	-12.4	6.92	0.157	18.0	19.9
C	-8.03	6.62	0.180	18.9	22.5
D	-2.93	7.1	1.059	36.0	40.2
E	-2.74	7.16	1.785	43.6	40.8
F	-2.02	6.72	0.865	33.5	48.5
G	11.33	5.96	0.206	19.9	21

FIGURE 9 Test 2 fracture surface striations.

CONCLUSIONS

This series of fatigue tests has shown that a moderate change in mode-mixity can be achieved with the cruciform test setup. In the presented tests, the deflection of a crack trajectory has been measured relative to trajectory of a purely mode-I loaded crack. A model, based on the MTS criterion, has predicted the crack trajectory to within 10% of the experimental result for the first 21% of the final crack length at the point of failure. At greater crack lengths, a correlation exists between deflection of the predicted trajectory and experimental result. The modelled specimen has provided a good prediction for the trajectory of two symmetrical cracks of equal growth rates. However, the asymmetric crack sizes of the experimental results could be better represented by modifying the MTS model to initiate cracks at different times in the life cycle. Striation counting via SEM imaging has provided an estimate of the experimental crack growth rate, which has been predicted by the MTS model with reasonable accuracy, despite the asymmetry of the cracks.

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REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Zerres, P., and Vormwald, M., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 58, 2014, pp. 75–83.
- (2) Erdogan, F., and Sih, G. C., *J. Fluids Eng. Trans. ASME*, Vol. 85, No. 4, 1963, pp. 519–525.
- (3) Shamsaei, N., and Fatemi, A., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 58, 2014, pp. 126–135.
- (4) Yu, X., and Li, L., *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, Vol. 174, 2017, pp. 155–167.
- (5) Mangardich, D., Abrari, F., and Fawaz, Z., *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, Vol. 214, 2019, pp. 474–486.
- (6) Barlow, K. W., and Chandra, R., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 27, 2005, pp. 1661–1668.
- (7) Byrne, J., Hall, R. F., and Powell, B. E., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 25, No. 9-11, 2003, pp. 827–834.
- (8) Witek, L., *Eng. Fail. Anal.*, Vol. 49, 2015, pp. 57–66.
- (9) Dowling, N. E., *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 32, No. 12, 2009, pp. 1004–1019.
- (10) Carrion, P. E., Shamsaei, N., and Daniewicz, S. R., Moser, R. D., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 99, 2017, pp. 87–100.